

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE ISSUE OF DEVELOPING COGNITIVE PROCESSES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN AN EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. This article provides information about the methodological basis of educational clustering and its direct importance in the implementation of inclusive education, foreign experience, the current role of education among subjects, and its methodology.

Key words: cluster system, education, pedagogy, research, subject.

In our country, the problem of pedagogical education cluster and its implementation in practice has been studied in depth as a separate research object in recent years. In particular, the fact that the educational cluster is a new innovative direction in our pedagogy related to integration and continuity and its implementation in practice is a factor in training competitive personnel in pedagogical education has been highlighted to a certain extent in the studies of G.I.Muhamedov, Sh.Q.Mardonov, Sh.Botirova, Kh.Sultonov, S.Toshtemirova, N.Koshanova, and Q.Mahmudov [5]. In areas related to the problem, in particular: organizational and pedagogical factors of the continuing education system, mechanisms for improving the content and form of the education system by R. Eshchanov, G. Bobojonova, D. Bekchanov, M. Kuronov, R.A. Mahmudov, R.Sh. Ahliddinov, Yu.N. Abdullaeva; ensuring continuity and continuity in education, strengthening integration between types of education by B.S. Abdullaeva, N.Kh. Rakhmonkulova, D.Sh. Yakibova, M.I. Toshpulatova, A.A. Zhumanov, R.B. Adizov; ensuring interdisciplinary connections and organizational aspects of scientific and methodological cooperation of educational institutions are reflected in the scientific research of N.M. Abdullaeva, G.Sh. Fayzullaeva, O.K. Abdurakhmonov. Scientific and theoretical foundations of the organization of educational clusters in the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), in particular, the structure of territorial educational clusters and the development of mechanisms for their implementation in practice, the problems of implementing the cluster model in vocational education A. Yashevoy, B. Pugacheva, A.G. Granberg, M. Galushkina, A.V. Leontev; technologies for theoretical and scientific-methodological improvement of educational management using the cluster model N.V. Gorodnova, P.F. Anisimov, G.I. Ibragimov, D.L. Skipin, V.P. Panasyuk, N.Ye. Yegorov; the content, conditions and factors of integration of production and education using clusters N.A. Mishura, L.L. Naumova; Integrated systems of organizing educational resources based on social cooperation that increase the capabilities of individual subjects and cluster participants were studied by A.S. Subetto, Ye.A. Korchagin, N.A. Sharay, L.N. Nikolaeva, T.V. Vdovina. In the scientific research of foreign scientists A. Marshall, M. Porter, O. Solvel, G. Lindqvist, S. Ketels, the role of the cluster model in increasing the competitiveness of certain entities, the unique typological features of the educational cluster model are revealed on the example of the USA and European countries. In foreign studies, educational clusters are generally studied in such areas as territoriality, management, competitiveness, science and production relations. The need to implement the cluster model as a factor affecting efficiency in a specific branch of education, in particular, pedagogical education, determined the topic of our research [4].

The cluster system unites entities that each carry out its own activities around a common goal, and at the same time, each entity acts on the basis of its own interests, proceeding from a common goal. The entities of the cluster system support and control each other, each of which creates a spiritual and intellectual space for a separate cluster, expanding its social impact and significance. Effective mechanisms and innovative technologies for preparing future specialists for professional activity have been implemented in the world education system [1]. As a result, the opportunity to model a modernized system of providing quality education through rapid diagnostics of the academic and social needs of the learner has expanded. Based on the “Incheon” Declaration adopted by the international organization UNESCO, “Lifelong Education” and “Education for All” programs, systematic work is being carried out to achieve inclusive education through the early involvement of children with disabilities in education, to improve the methods of teaching subjects in higher education and to provide practical guidance, and to intensively develop the professional competencies of future defectologists.

In world higher education and research institutions, scientific research is being conducted to develop methodologies for teaching children with disabilities in the process of inclusive and remedial education, diversify the activities of educational participants, improve the technologies of methodological preparation of future defectologists for professional practice, and identify effective mechanisms for increasing the participation of families and partner organizations in the educational process. Leading countries in the USA, China, Japan, France, Germany, Singapore, and Russia pay special attention to the use of interactive methods, effective use of adaptive teaching aids in preparing future defectologists, parents, and narrow specialists for the practice of remedial and inclusive education, the creation of didactic support for optimizing communicative-motivational, reflexive-developing requirements for the content of preschool and school education, improving pedagogical mechanisms for preparing students for mentor-teacher, mentor-student, partner-family activities, as well as systematizing technologies for preparing children with special needs for social life. An educational cluster is a system of a network of educational organizations aimed at developing priority socio-economic sectors of regions and municipalities, improving the quality of the educational process in the interests of the intellectual development of the younger generation. In particular, an educational cluster, as a rule, helps to unite and solve problems within the framework of fundamental scientific and scientific-practical developments, educational projects, new technologies and techniques, design and production of scientific products in the region.

List of used literature

1. Мухамедов Ф.И., Ходжамкулов У.Н. Педагогик таълим инновацион кластери: таъриф, тавсиф, тасниф. – Т.: Университет, 2019.
2. Питюков В.Ю. Основны педагогической технологии. – М.: Гном-Пресс, 1999.
3. Поулсеи С. Введение в современную методику преподавания. – Б.: Кесип, 2007.
4. Рахмонов А.Р. Инновацион таълим кластери ўқув фаолиятига самарали усул сифатида // Барқарор ривожланишда узлуксиз таълим: муаммо ва ечимлар. – Ч., 2019.
5. Файзуллаева Н.С. Таълим тизимида стратегик бошқарувнинг амалий аҳамиятлари // Иқтисодиёт ва инновацион технологиялар. – Т., 2012. – 5-сон. 2012.
6. Ходжамкулов У.Н. Таълим кластери инновация сифатида // Барқарор ривожланишда узлуксиз таълим: муаммо ва ечимлар: Халқаро илмий-амалий анжуман илмий ишлар тўплами. – Ч., 2019. – II-қисм.